

NAÏVE BAYES ALGORITHM BASED ON FORWARD SELECTION ON THE GRADUATION PREDICT OF TIME

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ABSTRACT

The number of students who do not pass on time, becomes a separate paradigm for institutions of higher education that must be handled properly, because in addition to affect the performance and lecturer ratio in the institution also brings a bad impact for the college. Therefore, timely graduation calculation for students is an important element in strategic decision making for an institution of higher education. Limitations in this research is on the comparison of calculation accuracy using Naive Bayes algorithm with calculation using Naive Bayes algorithm based on Forward Selection. The calculation result using Naive Bayes algorithm has 97,69% precision and accuracy on calculation using Naive Bayes-based Forward Selection algorithm produce better accuracy value that is 97,92%, so it can be concluded that the use of Naive Bayes Algorithm based on Forward Selection has the highest accuracy value with a precision 98,92%, and becomes the best model in problem solving in timely graduation predictions for students.

Keywords ; *Naive Bayes; Forward Selection; Graduation Prediction*

1. INTRODUCTION

The prediction of student graduation is very important for universities related to policies in decision making and evaluation of student performance. The evaluation results are stored in academic databases which can later be used as one indicator of educational efficiency in the institution. Prediction in this student graduation study is divided into 2, namely "Pass On Time" which means that students can complete their education in accordance with the institution's academic calendar, and "Pass Not Timely" which means that students complete their education longer or not in accordance with the academic calendar which is indicated by the institution of higher education. Based on the background described above, a problem can be formulated, namely higher education institution policy making related to timely and not timely graduation of students using the Naive Bayes algorithm can be maximized the level of accuracy with the addition of the Forward Selection feature.

The purpose of this study was to determine the accuracy of the Naive Bayes method in predicting student graduation and the accuracy of the Naive Bayes method by adding the Forward Selection feature to produce higher accuracy in predicting student graduation

This research will be useful for:

1. Providing an overview of the predictions of students who graduate not on time to higher education institutions, so that more intensive counseling can be carried out
2. The results of this study are expected to contribute to the prediction model with a data mining algorithm approach for the prediction of students who are Right and Not Timely in Graduation at the level of College as a scientific contribution

2. LITERATUR REVIEW

There are several studies on prediction of graduation or achievement using various models / methods as analysis based on historical data:

Diana Laeli and Eko Darmanto, 2014 "Decision support system for predicting student graduation using the naïve bayes method".

In this study the results achieved have an accuracy for on time of 93% and accuracy for being late at 71% by using the Naïve Bayes method which is increasingly optimal by determining students to graduate on time or late.

Marselina Suhartinah, Ernastuti, 2010 "Graduation Prediction Of Gunadharma University Studens Using Alaiith Bayes and C45 Algorithm". The accuracy of the prediction accuracy of C45 is 85.7% with an error value in the study using C45 reaching 14.3%. And testing using the Naive Bayes algorithm gets an accuracy value of 80.85%.

Erman Yukselturk, Turkey, 2012 "Predicting Dropout Student an Application of Data Mining Methods in Online Education Program". Datasheet testing uses several algorithms as follows: K-Neirest Neighbor (KNN) gets an accuracy value of 87% using Decision Tree, the accuracy level is 79.7% while using Naive Bayes Algorithm produces 76.8% accuracy and uses Neural Network algorithm produce an accuracy rate of 73.9%. The results above are maximized and produce the greatest accuracy level of 88.02% using Naive Bayes Algorithm with backward selection features.

Theoretical basis

Prediction is estimating something that will happen in the future. Prediction is obtained through scientific methods and only subjective. Prediction can also be used in classification, not only to predict time series, because it can produce classes based on various attributes.

Student graduation marks the end of students in completing education at the undergraduate level. Graduation is also the end result of a proud achievement in taking an education at a certain level. Bayes classification is also known as Naïve Bayes, has capabilities comparable to decision trees and neural networks.

$$P(x|y) = \frac{P(y|x)P(x)}{P(y)}$$

Information :

y = data with an unknown class

x = the data hypothesis y is a specific class

$P(x|y)$ = probability of hypothesis x based on condition y (posteriori probability)

$P(x)$ = probabilitas hipotesis x (*prior probability*)

$P(y|x)$ = probabilitas y based condition from x hypotesis

$P(y)$ = probabilitas from y

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The stages in this study are as follows:

- a. Data collection
- b. Initial data processing
- c. Grouping
- d. Stages of the proposed method
- e. Model Experiments and Testing
- f. Research evaluation and validation
- g. Results of Research Accuracy

The method proposed in this study is Forward Selection-based Naive Bayes Algorithm to predict the graduation on time for Polytechnic Harapan Bersama students are the steps in this study;

1. Calculating Prior Probability of each class or label.
2. Calculating the Probability of Hypotheses (Posteriori Probability)
3. Calculate the same number of cases with the same class:
 - a. Training

The Training Set contains records that have a class label used to build a classification model and are applied to a Test Set that contains records with labels that are not yet known.
 - b. Clasification

Determination of Classification is done by calculating the maximum value from $P(C_i | X)$ from data $P = \{p(C_i | X)\}$
 Calculation of probability $P(C_i | X)$ (test data) is considered as the result of the multiplication of probability of occurrence of C_i data.
 - c. Comparing Class Result

This stage compares the results of graduation determination both on time and not on time so that one graduation prediction is obtained with better accuracy.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data used in this study is data from POLITEKNIK HARAPAN BERSAMA Tegal . Data collected in this study was taken from graduation data from 2010 to 2013 as many as 1777 data records consisting of 90% training data totaling 1600 records and 10% data testing a total of 177 records with Nim attributes, Gender, Marriage Status, Job Status , IPS score 1 to IPS 4, and exact / late information.

Table 4.1 Examples of datashets & Attributes

NIM	M/F	MARITAL	JOB	IPS 1	IPS 2	IPS 3	IPS 4	PREDICTION
07040010	M	SINGLE	STUDENTS	3,35	2,71	2,77	2,58	...

The following are the graduation prediction steps for students with NIM 07040010 Politeknik Harapan Bersama Tegal

A. RIGHT TIME

1. $P(\text{student on time} / \text{total student}) * P(\text{male} / \text{on time}) * P(\text{student} / \text{on time}) * P(\text{unmarried} / \text{on time}) * P(3.35 / \text{IPS } 1 > 3.0 \text{ on time}) * P(2.71 / \text{IPS } 2 > 2.0 \text{ on time}) * P(2.77 / \text{IPS } 3 > 2.0 \text{ on time}) * P(2.58 / \text{IPS } 4 > 2.0 \text{ on time})$
2. Thus, $0.93 * 0.42 * 0.98 * 0.98 * 0.06 * 0.08 * 0.12 * 0.28 = 0,00060$

B. NOT TIMELY

1. $P(\text{students are not on time} / \text{total students}) * P(\text{male} / \text{not on time}) * P(\text{student} / \text{not on time}) * P(\text{unmarried} / \text{not on time}) * P(\text{IPS } 1) * P(\text{IPS } 2) * P(\text{IPS } 3) * P(\text{IPS } 4)$
2. Thus, $0,21 * 0,98 * 0,98 * 0,47 * 0,27 * 0,47 * 0,19 * 0,076 = 0,00006$

C. DETERMINATION OF PREDICTION

Timely Prediction = 0,00060

Timely Prediction = 0.00006

Prediction = $0,00060 > 0,00006$

Become a prediction of students with NIM 07040010 Politeknik Harapan Bersama Tegal, is **TIME**

The experiment was carried out by looking at the performance of the Naive Bayes algorithm after getting prediction data. Tests carried out cross validation (cross validation) as much as 10 times (10 vold validation), which is by dividing the test data into 10 sub samples with a test data ratio starting from 10% with the same increase up to 90%. Each ratio is carried out 10 times with the expected output is the average Accuracy.

The following is the calculation of the test level of accuracy in 10 fold Cross Validation

$$\begin{aligned} \text{a. Accuracy} &= \frac{TP + TN}{TP+FN+FP+TN} \\ &= \frac{(1641+99)}{(1641+18+19+99)} \\ &= 97,92\% \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{b. Sensitivity} &= \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \\ &= \frac{(1641)}{(1641+19)} \\ &= 98,86\% \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{c. Specifity} &= \frac{TN}{FN+TN} \\ &= \frac{(99)}{(18+99)} \\ &= 84,62\% \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{d. Precision} &= \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \\ &= \frac{(1641)}{(1641+18)} \\ &= 98,92\% \end{aligned}$$

From the above discussion we can see the results of the performance comparison of the Naive Bayes Algorithm on the prediction of graduation on time and not on time with the results of the performance of Forward Selections Naive Bayes Algorithm, which is described in the following table:

Table 4.1 Research Results

Model	Accuracy	Precision
Naive Bayes	97,69 %	80,08 %
Naive Bayes – Forward Selections	97,92 %	98,92 %

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

From the results of the study using data mining classification algorithms namely Forward Selection-based Naive Bayes to predict the exact or not timely graduation of students by using 1777 data sets of the Harapan Bersama Tegal Polytechnic students, it can be analyzed from the results that the addition selection feature in predictions can improve accuracy and entered into the excellent clasification section with an accuracy rate of 97.92% with a precision level of 98.92% compared to predictions using only the Naive Bayes algorithm, namely 97.68% For suggestions, the next research can add another data mining classification algorithm in addition to the main Naive Bayes algorithm, and it is expected to select attributes and because the validation of the data set is very important so as to produce a balanced accuracy with the method used.

5. CLOSING

The study was titled "BAYES NAÏVE ALGORITHM BASED ON FORWARD SELECTION IN TIMELY PASSAGE PREDICTION", this can be resolved well because of the support of various parties. For this reason, it is very important for the author to convey an unlimited thank you to;

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Finally, the author is very aware of the limitations in this study, so it is expected that there are criticisms and suggestions for improving research. May be useful.